

PRODUCT USER MANUAL

European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature
Climate Change Initiative

and

Copernicus Climate Change Service
L4 SST analyses

SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024

Issue: 2.3

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RECORD TABLE

Issue	Date	§	Description of Change	Author	Validated By
1.0	18 January 2017	All	First version, based on the ESA SST CCI Product User Guide	Simon Good	
1.1	16 March 2017	Title page, section I	Added ESA and SST CCI logos and license details.	Simon Good	
2.0	12 April 2019		ESA SST CCI updated to version CDR2.0.	Simon Good	
2.1	10 September 2019		C3S ICDR2.0 added.	Simon Good	
2.2	10 September 2020	All	Document extension to 2019 and update document template.	Simon Good	
2.3	15 January 2021	II.1,II.4	Temporal extensions.	Simon Good	C. Derval

CONTENT

GLOSSARY AND ABBREVIATIONS	4
I INTRODUCTION	5
I.1 Summary	5
I.2 History of changes	6
II PRODUCT DESCRIPTION: SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024	7
II.1 General Information about products	7
II.2 Details of the datasets	8
II.3 Product System Description	9
II.4 Processing information	11
II.4.1 Update Time.....	11
II.4.2 Time coverage.....	11
II.4.3 Time averaging.....	11
III HOW TO DOWNLOAD A PRODUCT	12
III.1 Download a product through the CMEMS Web Portal Subsetter Service	12
III.2 Download a product through the CMEMS Web Portal Ftp Service	12
IV FILES NOMENCLATURE and FORMAT	13
IV.1 Nomenclature of files when downloaded through the Subsetter Service	13
IV.2 Nomenclature of files when downloaded through the DGF and CMEMS FTP Services	13
IV.3 File Format: netCDF	14
IV.4 File size	14
IV.5 Remember: scale_factor & add_offset / missing_value / land mask	14
IV.6 Reading Software	15
IV.7 Structure and semantic of netCDF maps files	15

GLOSSARY AND ABBREVIATIONS

C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CCI	Climate Change Initiative
CF	Climate Forecast (convention for netCDF)
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
ESA	European Space Agency
ftp	Protocol to download files
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
OpenDAP	Open-Source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol. Protocol to download subset of data from a n-dimensional gridded dataset (ie: 4 dimensions: lon-lat,depth,time)
OSTIA	Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis
PU	Production Unit
SST	Sea surface temperature
Subsetter	CMEMS service tool to download a NetCDF file of a selected geographical box using values of longitude an latitude, and time range

I INTRODUCTION

I.1 Summary

This is the Product User Manual describing the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative (ESA SST CCI) and Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) analysis (level 4) product over the global ocean (SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024) [RD.1], which was processed at the Met Office and at the JASMIN facility (<http://www.jasmin.ac.uk/>) as part of those projects. The data can be accessed through CMEMS in addition to the dissemination methods provided by the originators. This manual covers: how it was created, its content, and which data services are available to access it through CMEMS.

The ESA SST CCI and C3S reprocessed analysis product is a satellite SST analysis created using the OSTIA (Operational SST and Sea Ice Analysis) system from re-processed (A)ATSR, SLSTR and AVHRR data. Its key features include its stability and its independence from in situ data.

The ESA SST CCI data cover from 1st September 1981 to 31st December 2016 and the C3S data from 1st January 2017 onwards. Data are on a global regular grid at 0.05° resolution. The product provides an estimate of the SST at 20 cm. The inputs to the system are SSTs at 10:30 am and pm local time which means that the analyses roughly correspond to the daily average SST.

Products are made available under a Creative Commons Attribution license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). This allows the sharing and adaptation of the data for any purpose as long as appropriate credit is given, a link to the license is provided and an indication of any changes made to the data is provided.

As such please take note of these points (adapted from http://licences.ceda.ac.uk/image/data_access_condition/esacci_sst_terms_and_conditions.pdf):

1. Users of the data are required to acknowledge the ESA Climate Change Initiative and the SST CCI project together with the individual data providers if the data are used in a presentation or publication. Please also cite any relevant dataset DOIs.
2. Users of the data are encouraged to interact with the CCI programmes on use of the products, and to provide a copy of all reports and publications using the dataset. An offer of co-authorship should be considered, if the CCI data constitute a major component of a scientific publication.
3. Intellectual property rights (IPR) in the data lie with the researchers and organisations producing the data.
4. Liability: No warranty is given as to the quality or the accuracy of the data or its suitability for any use. All implied conditions relating to the quality or suitability of the information, and all liabilities arising from the supply of the information (including any liability arising in negligence) are excluded to the fullest extent permitted by law.

Please cite the following dataset paper and the relevant dataset DOI (see below for an example).

Dataset paper:

Merchant, C.J., Embury, O., Bulgin, C.E., Block, T., Corlett, G.K., Fiedler, E., Good, S.A., Mittaz, J., Rayner, N.A., Berry, D., Eastwood, S., Taylor, M., Tsushima, Y., Waterfall, A., Wilson, R. and Donlon, C. (2019), Satellite-based time-series of sea-surface temperature since 1981 for climate applications. Scientific Data 6, 223, doi:10.1038/s41597-019-0236-x

Example dataset DOI citation:

Good, S.A.; Embury, O.; Bulgin, C.E.; Mittaz, J. (2019): ESA Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative (SST_cci): Level 4 Analysis Climate Data Record, version 2.0. Centre for Environmental Data Analysis, 22 August 2019. doi:10.5285/aced40d7cb964f23a0fd3e85772f2d48

More information about this product can be found in:

The production system and the quality of the analyses are summarised in the Quality Information Document (QuID) - <http://marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CMEMS-GLO-QUID-001-024.pdf>.

The ESA SST CCI Product User Guide [RD.2] at is available at http://www.esa-sst-cci.org/PUG/pdf/SST_CCI-PUG-UKMO-201_Issue_2-signed.pdf.

The C3S documentation, including the licensing information, can be accessed at <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/satellite-sea-surface-temperature?tab=doc>.

Specific queries can be directed to the CMEMS Service Desk (servicedesk.cmems@mercator-ocean.eu).

I.2 History of changes

Date	Description of changes and impacted product
<u>INITIAL VERSION</u>	The initial version provided through CMEMS was version 1.1 of the ESA SST CCI processing (version 1.0 contained some problems in the sea ice fields; these were corrected in version 1.1).
<u>JULY 2019</u>	ESA SST CCI analyses were updated to version CDR2.0.
<u>DECEMBER 2019</u>	The C3S ICDR2.0 analyses were added to the product.
<u>DECEMBER 2020</u>	2019 added to the dataset.
<u>MAY 2021</u>	Monthly temporal extensions.

II PRODUCT DESCRIPTION: SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024

II.1 General Information about products

Product name	SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024		
Geographical coverage	Global		
Variables	Sea surface temperature Sea surface temperature uncertainty Ice area fraction Mask		
Analysis / Update frequency	No		
Multi-Year/ Frequency Update	Reprocessing	Yearly	
Available time series	01/09/1981 – approx. 3-4 months behind real time		
Temporal resolution	Daily		
Horizontal resolution	1/20 ° (regular grid)		
Number of vertical levels	Surface only		
Format	NetCDF CF-1.5, Unidata Observation Dataset v1.0		
Delivery mechanisms	Subsetter	WMS	FTP

II.2 Details of the datasets

SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024
C3S-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBS-SST/ESACCI-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBS-SST contains
analysed_sst [K] analysed sea surface temperature sea_water_temperature
analysis_uncertainty [K] estimated error standard deviation of analysed_sst sea_water_temperature standard_error
sea_ice_fraction sea ice area fraction sea_ice_area_fraction
mask land sea ice lake bit mask

II.3 Product System Description

Figure II.1 Schematic diagram of the reprocessing chain used for the processing.

The Operational Sea Surface Temperature and Ice Analysis (OSTIA) reprocessing system has been run at the Met Office and the JASMIN facility to produce the analyses. Figure II.1 shows the different steps for the creation of the reprocessed products. Key information is provided in the table below.

Domain Resolution and grid Geographic coverage	<p>GLOBAL (180°W-180°E ; 90°S – 90°N) with 1 time step per file 1/20° ; regular grid ; 7200 x 3600 x 1</p> <p>SST, SST uncertainty, ice concentration and mask variables are provided on global, spatially complete (excluding lakes), regular grids.</p>
Version	(I)CDR2.0
Assimilation scheme	NEMOVAR
Assimilated observations	<p>SST input data were L3U AVHRR, (A)ATSR and SLSTR data produced by the ESA SST CCI and C3S projects. The projects provide data that have been adjusted to 20 cm depth and 10.30 local time and these are used in the L4 processing.</p> <p>Ice concentration data from the EUMETSAT OSI-SAF are used in the OSTIA reprocessing. Products used are:</p> <p>OSI-450 - EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility. Global sea ice concentration climate data record 1979-2015 (v2.0, 2017), [Online]. Norwegian and Danish Meteorological Institutes. doi: 10.15770/EUM_SAF_OSI_0008. [RD.6]</p> <p>OSI-430 - EUMETSAT Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility. Global sea ice concentration continuous reprocessing offline product (2018), [Online]. Norwegian and Danish Meteorological Institutes. Available from https://osisaf-hl.met.no/.</p> <p>Reference: Lavergne, T., Sørensen, A. M., Kern, S., Tonboe, R., Notz, D., Aaboe, S., Bell, L., Dybkjær, G., Eastwood, S., Gabarro, C., Heygster, G., Killie, M. A., Brandt Kreiner, M., Lavelle, J., Saldo, R., Sandven, S., and Pedersen, L. T.: <i>Version 2 of the EUMETSAT OSI SAF and ESA CCI sea-ice concentration climate data records</i>, <i>The Cryosphere</i>, 13, 49-78, doi:10.5194/tc-13-49-2019, 2019.</p>
Climatology	The SST climatologies used were derived from the v1.1 ESA SST CCI reprocessing

II.4 Processing information

II.4.1 Update Time

Analyses are updated monthly.

II.4.2 Time coverage

The analyses cover 1 September 1981 to 3-4 months behind real time.

II.4.3 Time averaging

Each daily SST analysis is based on three days of input data (the analysis day and the two surrounding days). The uncertainty in the surrounding day's data is increased to reduce their influence on the analyses compared to the data from the analysis day.

III HOW TO DOWNLOAD A PRODUCT

III.1 Download a product through the CMEMS Web Portal Subsetter Service

You first need to register. Please find below the registration steps:
<http://marine.copernicus.eu/web/34-products-and-services-faq.php#1>

Once registered, the CMEMS FAQ <http://marine.copernicus.eu/web/34-products-and-services-faq.php> will guide you on how to download a product through the CMEMS Web Portal Subsetter Service.

III.2 Download a product through the CMEMS Web Portal Ftp Service

You first need to register. Please find below the registration steps:
<http://marine.copernicus.eu/web/34-products-and-services-faq.php#1>

Once registered, the CMEMS FAQ <http://marine.copernicus.eu/web/34-products-and-services-faq.php> will guide you on how to download a product through the CMEMS Web Portal FTP Service.

IV FILES NOMENCLATURE AND FORMAT

IV.1 Nomenclature of files when downloaded through the Subsetter Service

Files nomenclature when downloaded through the CMEMS Web Portal Subsetter is based on product dataset name and a numerical reference related to the request date on the portal.

The scheme is: **datasetname-nnnnnnnnnnnnn.nc**

where :

.datasetname is a character string:

ESACCI-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBS-SST

C3S-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBS-SST

. nnnnnnnnnnnnn: 13 digit integer corresponding to the current time (download time) in milliseconds since January 1, 1970 midnight UTC.

.nc: standard NetCDF filename extension.

Example:

ESACCI-GLO-SST-L4_REP-OBS-SST_1303461772348.nc

IV.2 Nomenclature of files when downloaded through the DGF and CMEMS FTP Services

Files nomenclature when downloaded through the CMEMS FTP is based on the date, data source and data record version.

The scheme is: <date>120000-<source>-L4_GHRSSST-SSTdepth-OSTIA-GLOB_<version>-v02.0-fv01.0.nc

Where:

- Date: integer (format YYYYMMDD) corresponding to the analysis date
- Source: data producer (either ESACCI or C3S)
- Version: data record version (either CDR2.0 or ICDR2.0, for data producer ESACCI or C3S respectively)

Examples:

20060326120000-ESACCI-L4_GHRSSST-SSTdepth-OSTIA-GLOB_CDR2.0-v02.0-fv01.0.nc

20171223120000-C3S-L4_GHRSSST-SSTdepth-OSTIA-GLOB_ICDR2.0-v02.0-fv01.0.nc

IV.3 File Format: netCDF

The products are stored using the netCDF format.

NetCDF (network Common Data Form) is an interface for array-oriented data access and a library that provides an implementation of the interface. The netCDF library also defines a machine-independent format for representing scientific data. Together, the interface, library, and format support the creation, access, and sharing of scientific data. The netCDF software was developed at the Unidata Program Center in Boulder, Colorado. The netCDF libraries define a machine-independent format for representing scientific data.

Please see Unidata netCDF pages for more information, and to retrieve NetCDF software package.

NetCDF data is:

- * Self-Describing. A netCDF file includes information about the data it contains.
- * Architecture-independent. A netCDF file is represented in a form that can be accessed by computers with different ways of storing integers, characters, and floating-point numbers.
- * Direct-access. A small subset of a large dataset may be accessed efficiently, without first reading through all the preceding data.
- * Appendable. Data can be appended to a netCDF dataset along one dimension without copying the dataset or redefining its structure. The structure of a netCDF dataset can be changed, though this sometimes causes the dataset to be copied.
- * Sharable. One writer and multiple readers may simultaneously access the same netCDF file.

IV.4 File size

DATASET NAME	FILE NAME	DIMENSION [MB]	
		Compressed	Uncompressed
SST-GLO-SST-L4-REP-OBSERVATIONS-010-024	<date>120000-<source>-L4_GHRSST-SSTdepth-OSTIA-GLOB_<version>-v02.0-fv01.0.nc	16	16

IV.5 Remember: scale_factor & add_offset / missing_value / land mask

Real_Value = (Display_Value X scale_factor) + add_offset

The missing value for this product is: -32768s (analysed_sst and analysis_uncertainty) or -128b (sea_ice_fraction and mask).

Land locations are set to the missing value, which is stored as the “_FillValue” variable attribute in the files.

IV.6 Reading Software

NetCDF data can be browsed and used through a number of software, like:

- ✓ ncBrowse: <http://www.epic.noaa.gov/java/ncBrowse/>,
- ✓ NetCDF Operator (NCO): <http://nco.sourceforge.net/>
- ✓ IDL, Matlab, GMT...

Useful information on UNIDATA: <http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>

IV.7 Structure and semantic of netCDF maps files

Example header of an ESA SST CCI L4 netCDF file (generated using ncdump) is given below.

```
netcdf \20060326120000-ESACCI-L4_GHRSSST-SSTdepth-OSTIA-GLOB_CDR2.0-v02.0-fv01.0 {
```

```
dimensions:
```

```
time = 1 ;  
lat = 3600 ;  
lon = 7200 ;
```

```
variables:
```

```
int time(time) ;  
    time:long_name = "reference time of sst field" ;  
    time:standard_name = "time" ;  
    time:axis = "T" ;  
    time:units = "seconds since 1981-01-01 00:00:00" ;  
    time:comment = "" ;  
float lat(lat) ;  
    lat:standard_name = "latitude" ;  
    lat:long_name = "latitude" ;  
    lat:units = "degrees_north" ;  
    lat:valid_min = -90.f ;  
    lat:valid_max = 90.f ;  
    lat:axis = "Y" ;  
    lat:comment = " Latitude geographical coordinates,WGS84 projection" ;
```

```
float lon(lon) ;  
    lon:standard_name = "longitude" ;  
    lon:long_name = "longitude" ;  
    lon:units = "degrees_east" ;  
    lon:valid_min = -180.f ;  
    lon:valid_max = 180.f ;  
    lon:axis = "X" ;  
    lon:comment = " Longitude geographical coordinates,WGS84 projection" ;
```



```
short analysed_sst(time, lat, lon) ;
    analysed_sst:long_name = "analysed sea surface temperature" ;
    analysed_sst:standard_name = "sea_water_temperature" ;
    analysed_sst:units = "kelvin" ;
    analysed_sst:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
    analysed_sst:_FillValue = -32768s ;
    analysed_sst:add_offset = 273.15f ;
    analysed_sst:scale_factor = 0.01f ;
    analysed_sst:valid_min = -300s ;
    analysed_sst:valid_max = 4500s ;
    analysed_sst:source = "ATSR<1,2>-ESACCI-L3U-v2.0, AATSR-ESACCI-L3U-v2.0,
AVHRR<06,07,08,09,10,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19>-G-ESACCI-L2P-v2.0, AVHRRMTA-ESACCI-L2P-v2.0" ;
short analysis_uncertainty(time, lat, lon) ;
    analysis_uncertainty:long_name = "estimated error standard deviation of analysed_sst" ;
    analysis_uncertainty:standard_name = "sea_water_temperature_standard_error" ;
    analysis_uncertainty:units = "kelvin" ;
    analysis_uncertainty:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
    analysis_uncertainty:_FillValue = -32768s ;
    analysis_uncertainty:add_offset = 0.f ;
    analysis_uncertainty:scale_factor = 0.01f ;
    analysis_uncertainty:valid_min = 0s ;
    analysis_uncertainty:valid_max = 32767s ;
byte sea_ice_fraction(time, lat, lon) ;
    sea_ice_fraction:long_name = "sea ice area fraction" ;
    sea_ice_fraction:standard_name = "sea_ice_area_fraction" ;
    sea_ice_fraction:units = "1" ;
    sea_ice_fraction:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
    sea_ice_fraction:_FillValue = -128b ;
    sea_ice_fraction:add_offset = 0.f ;
    sea_ice_fraction:scale_factor = 0.01f ;
    sea_ice_fraction:valid_min = 0b ;
    sea_ice_fraction:valid_max = 100b ;
    sea_ice_fraction:source = "ESA Sea Ice CCI" ;
    sea_ice_fraction:comment = " Sea ice area fraction" ;
byte mask(time, lat, lon) ;
    mask:long_name = "land sea ice lake bit mask" ;
    mask:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
    mask:_FillValue = -128b ;
    mask:valid_min = 1b ;
    mask:valid_max = 31b ;
    mask:flag_masks = 1b, 2b, 4b, 8b, 16b ;
    mask:flag_meanings = "water land optional_lake_surface sea_ice optional_river_surface" ;
    mask:source = "NAVOCEANO_landmask_v1.0 EUMETSAT_OSI-SAF_icemask
ARCLake_lakemask" ;
```



```
mask:comment = " Land/ open ocean/ sea ice /lake mask" ;

// global attributes:
:Conventions = "CF-1.5, Unidata Observation Dataset v1.0" ;
:title = "ESA SST CCI OSTIA L4 product" ;
:summary = "OSTIA L4 product from the ESA SST CCI project, produced using OSTIA reanalysis
system v3.0" ;
:references = "http://www.esa-sst-cci.org" ;
:institution = "ESACCI" ;
:history = "Created using OSTIA reanalysis system v3.0" ;
:comment = "These data were produced at the Met Office as part of the ESA SST CCI project.
WARNING Some applications are unable to properly handle signed byte values. If values are
encountered > 127, please subtract 256
from this reported value" ;
:license = "Creative Commons Licence by attribution
(https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)" ;
:id = "OSTIA-ESACCI-L4-GLOB-v2.0" ;
:naming_authority = "org.ghrsst" ;
:product_version = "2.0" ;
:uuid = "7fdf2639-26e5-4d4f-a60e-0bcfc9744204" ;
:tracking_id = "7fdf2639-26e5-4d4f-a60e-0bcfc9744204" ;
:gds_version_id = "2.0" ;
:netcdf_version_id = "4.2.1.1 of Oct 19 2012 14:25:16" ;
:date_created = "20180627T160903Z" ;
:file_quality_level = 3 ;
:spatial_resolution = "0.05 degree" ;
:start_time = "20060326T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_start = "20060326T000000Z" ;
:stop_time = "20060327T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "20060327T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_duration = "P1D" ;
:time_coverage_resolution = "P1D" ;
:northernmost_latitude = 90.f ;
:geospatial_lat_max = 90.f ;
:southernmost_latitude = -90.f ;
:geospatial_lat_min = -90.f ;
:easternmost_longitude = 180.f ;
:geospatial_lon_max = 180.f ;
:westernmost_longitude = -180.f ;
:geospatial_lon_min = -180.f ;
:geospatial_vertical_min = -0.2f ;
:geospatial_vertical_max = -0.2f ;
:source = "ATSR<1,2>-ESACCI-L3U-v2.0, AATSR-ESACCI-L3U-v2.0,
AVHRR<06,07,08,09,10,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19>-G-ESACCI-L2P-v2.0, AVHRRMTA-ESACCI-L2P-v2.0,
ESACCI-ICE-v2" ;
```



```
:platform = "ERS-<1,2>, Envisat, NOAA-<06,07,08,09,10,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19>, MetOpA" ;
:sensor = "ATSR, AATSR, AVHRR_GAC" ;
:Metadata_Conventions = "Unidata Dataset Discovery v1.0" ;
:metadata_link = "http://www.esa-cci.org" ;
:keywords = "Oceans > Ocean Temperature > Sea Surface Temperature" ;
:keywords_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords" ;
:standard_name_vocabulary = "NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention" ;
:geospatial_lat_units = "degrees_north" ;
:geospatial_lat_resolution = 0.05f ;
:geospatial_lon_units = "degrees_east" ;
:geospatial_lon_resolution = 0.05f ;
:acknowledgment = "Funded by ESA" ;
:creator_name = "SST_cci" ;
:creator_email = "science.leader@esa-sst-cci.org" ;
:creator_processing_institution = "These data were produced at the Met Office as part of the
ESA SST CCI project." ;
mask:long_name = "land sea ice lake bit mask" ;
mask:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
mask:_FillValue = -128b ;
mask:valid_min = 1b ;
mask:valid_max = 31b ;
mask:flag_masks = 1b, 2b, 4b, 8b, 16b ;
mask:flag_meanings = "water land optional_lake_surface sea_ice optional_river_surface" ;
mask:source = "NAVOCEANO_landmask_v1.0 EUMETSAT_OSI-SAF_icemask
ARCLake_lakemask" ;
mask:comment = " Land/ open ocean/ sea ice /lake mask" ;

// global attributes:
:Conventions = "CF-1.5, Unidata Observation Dataset v1.0" ;
:title = "ESA SST CCI OSTIA L4 product" ;
:summary = "OSTIA L4 product from the ESA SST CCI project, produced using OSTIA reanalysis
system v3.0" ;
:references = "http://www.esa-sst-cci.org" ;
:institution = "ESACCI" ;
:history = "Created using OSTIA reanalysis system v3.0" ;
:comment = "These data were produced at the Met Office as part of the ESA SST CCI project.
WARNING Some applications are unable to properly handle signed byte values. If values are
encountered > 127, please subtract 256
from this reported value" ;
:license = "Creative Commons Licence by attribution
(https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)" ;
:id = "OSTIA-ESACCI-L4-GLOB-v2.0" ;
:naming_authority = "org.ghrsst" ;
:product_version = "2.0" ;
:uuid = "7fdf2639-26e5-4d4f-a60e-0bcfc9744204" ;
```



```
:tracking_id = "7fdf2639-26e5-4d4f-a60e-0bcfc9744204" ;
:gds_version_id = "2.0" ;
:netcdf_version_id = "4.2.1.1 of Oct 19 2012 14:25:16" ;
:date_created = "20180627T160903Z" ;
:file_quality_level = 3 ;
:spatial_resolution = "0.05 degree" ;
:start_time = "20060326T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_start = "20060326T000000Z" ;
:stop_time = "20060327T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "20060327T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_duration = "P1D" ;
:time_coverage_resolution = "P1D" ;
:northernmost_latitude = 90.f ;
:geospatial_lat_max = 90.f ;
:southernmost_latitude = -90.f ;
:geospatial_lat_min = -90.f ;
:easternmost_longitude = 180.f ;
:geospatial_lon_max = 180.f ;
:westernmost_longitude = -180.f ;
:geospatial_lon_min = -180.f ;
:geospatial_vertical_min = -0.2f ;
:geospatial_vertical_max = -0.2f ;
:source = "ATSR<1,2>-ESACCI-L3U-v2.0, AATSR-ESACCI-L3U-v2.0,
AVHRR<06,07,08,09,10,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19>-G-ESACCI-L2P-v2.0, AVHRRMTA-ESACCI-L2P-v2.0,
ESACCI-ICE-v2" ;
:platform = "ERS-<1,2>, Envisat, NOAA-<06,07,08,09,10,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,19>, MetOpA" ;
:sensor = "ATSR, AATSR, AVHRR_GAC" ;
:Metadata_Conventions = "Unidata Dataset Discovery v1.0" ;
:metadata_link = "http://www.esa-cci.org" ;
:keywords = "Oceans > Ocean Temperature > Sea Surface Temperature" ;
:keywords_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords" ;
:standard_name_vocabulary = "NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention" ;
:geospatial_lat_units = "degrees_north" ;
:geospatial_lat_resolution = 0.05f ;
:geospatial_lon_units = "degrees_east" ;
:geospatial_lon_resolution = 0.05f ;
:acknowledgment = "Funded by ESA" ;
:creator_name = "SST_cci" ;
:creator_email = "science.leader@esa-sst-cci.org" ;
:creator_processing_institution = "These data were produced at the Met Office as part of the
ESA SST CCI project." ;
```

Example header of a C3S L4 netCDF file (generated using ncdump) is given below.

```
netcdf \20171212120000-C3S-L4_GHRSST-SSTdepth-OSTIA-GLOB_ICDR2.0-v02.0-fv01.0 {
```


dimensions:

```
time = 1 ;  
lat = 3600 ;  
lon = 7200 ;
```

variables:

```
int time(time) ;  
    time:long_name = "reference time of sst field" ;  
    time:standard_name = "time" ;  
    time:axis = "T" ;  
    time:units = "seconds since 1981-01-01 00:00:00" ;  
    time:comment = ;  
float lat(lat) ;  
    lat:standard_name = "latitude" ;  
    lat:long_name = "latitude" ;  
    lat:units = "degrees_north" ;  
    lat:valid_min = -90.f ;  
    lat:valid_max = 90.f ;  
    lat:axis = "Y" ;  
    lat:comment = " Latitude geographical coordinates,WGS84 projection" ;  
float lon(lon) ;  
    lon:standard_name = "longitude" ;  
    lon:long_name = "longitude" ;  
    lon:units = "degrees_east" ;  
    lon:valid_min = -180.f ;  
    lon:valid_max = 180.f ;  
    lon:axis = "X" ;  
    lon:comment = " Longitude geographical coordinates,WGS84 projection" ;
```

```
short analysed_sst(time, lat, lon) ;  
    analysed_sst:long_name = "analysed sea surface temperature" ;  
    analysed_sst:standard_name = "sea_water_temperature" ;  
    analysed_sst:units = "kelvin" ;  
    analysed_sst:coordinates = "lon lat" ;  
    analysed_sst:_FillValue = -32768s ;  
    analysed_sst:add_offset = 273.15f ;  
    analysed_sst:scale_factor = 0.01f ;  
    analysed_sst:valid_min = -300s ;  
    analysed_sst:valid_max = 4500s ;  
    analysed_sst:source = "AVHRR19_G-C3S-L3U-ICDR-v2.0 AVHRRMTA_G-C3S-L3U-ICDR-v2.0  
SLSTRA-C3S-L3U-ICDR-v2.0" ;
```

```
short analysis_uncertainty(time, lat, lon) ;  
    analysis_uncertainty:long_name = "estimated error standard deviation of analysed_sst" ;  
    analysis_uncertainty:standard_name = "sea_water_temperature_standard_error" ;  
    analysis_uncertainty:units = "kelvin" ;  
    analysis_uncertainty:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
```



```
analysis_uncertainty:_FillValue = -32768s ;
analysis_uncertainty:add_offset = 0.f ;
analysis_uncertainty:scale_factor = 0.01f ;
analysis_uncertainty:valid_min = 0s ;
analysis_uncertainty:valid_max = 32767s ;
byte sea_ice_fraction(time, lat, lon) ;
  sea_ice_fraction:long_name = "sea ice area fraction" ;
  sea_ice_fraction:standard_name = "sea_ice_area_fraction" ;
  sea_ice_fraction:units = "1" ;
  sea_ice_fraction:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
  sea_ice_fraction:_FillValue = -128b ;
  sea_ice_fraction:add_offset = 0.f ;
  sea_ice_fraction:scale_factor = 0.01f ;
  sea_ice_fraction:valid_min = 0b ;
  sea_ice_fraction:valid_max = 100b ;
  sea_ice_fraction:source = "EUMETSAT OSI SAF OSI-430" ;
  sea_ice_fraction:comment = " Sea ice area fraction" ;
byte mask(time, lat, lon) ;
  mask:long_name = "land sea ice lake bit mask" ;
  mask:coordinates = "lon lat" ;
  mask:_FillValue = -128b ;
  mask:valid_min = 1b ;
  mask:valid_max = 31b ;
  mask:flag_masks = 1b, 2b, 4b, 8b, 16b ;
  mask:flag_meanings = "water land optional_lake_surface sea_ice optional_river_surface" ;
  mask:source = "NAVOCEANO_landmask_v1.0 EUMETSAT_OSI-SAF_icemask
ARCLake_lakemask" ;
  mask:comment = " Land/ open ocean/ sea ice /lake mask" ;

// global attributes:
:Conventions = "CF-1.5, Unidata Observation Dataset v1.0" ;
:title = "C3S SST L4 product" ;
:summary = "OSTIA L4 product from the C3S project, produced using OSTIA reanalysis system
v3.0" ;
:references = "http://www.esa-sst-cci.org" ;
:institution = "C3S" ;
:history = "Created using OSTIA reanalysis system v3.0" ;
:comment = "These data were produced by the Met Office as part of the C3S project.
WARNING Some applications are unable to properly handle signed byte values. If values are
encountered > 127, please subtract 256 from the
is reported value" ;
:license = "Creative Commons Licence by attribution
(https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)" ;
:id = "OSTIA-C3S-L4-GLOB-v2.0" ;
:naming_authority = "org.ghrsst" ;
```



```
:product_version = "2.0" ;
:uuid = "7fdf2639-26e5-4d4f-a60e-0bcfc9744204" ;
:tracking_id = "7fdf2639-26e5-4d4f-a60e-0bcfc9744204" ;
:gds_version_id = "2.0" ;
:netcdf_version_id = "4.2.1.1 of Oct 19 2012 14:25:16" ;
:date_created = "20181009T15:25:11Z" ;
:creation_date = "2018-10-09T15:25:11Z" ;
:file_quality_level = 3 ;
:spatial_resolution = "0.05 degree" ;
:start_time = "20171212T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_start = "20171212T000000Z" ;
:stop_time = "20171213T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "20171213T000000Z" ;
:time_coverage_duration = "P1D" ;
:time_coverage_resolution = "P1D" ;
:northernmost_latitude = 90.f ;
:geospatial_lat_max = 90.f ;
:southernmost_latitude = -90.f ;
:geospatial_lat_min = -90.f ;
:easternmost_longitude = 180.f ;
:geospatial_lon_max = 180.f ;
:westernmost_longitude = -180.f ;
:geospatial_lon_min = -180.f ;
:geospatial_vertical_min = -0.2f ;
:geospatial_vertical_max = -0.2f ;
:source = "AVHRR19_G-C3S-L3U-ICDR-v2.0 AVHRRMTA_G-C3S-L3U-ICDR-v2.0 SLSTRA-C3S-
L3U-ICDR-v2.0, OSI-430" ;
:platform = "NOAA-19, MetOpA, Sentinel-3A" ;
:sensor = "AVHRR_GAC, SLSTR" ;
:Metadata_Conventions = "Unidata Dataset Discovery v1.0" ;
:metadata_link = "http://www.esa-cci.org" ;
:keywords = "Oceans > Ocean Temperature > Sea Surface Temperature" ;
:keywords_vocabulary = "NASA Global Change Master Directory (GCMD) Science Keywords" ;
:standard_name_vocabulary = "NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Convention" ;
:geospatial_lat_units = "degrees_north" ;
:geospatial_lat_resolution = 0.05f ;
:geospatial_lon_units = "degrees_east" ;
:geospatial_lon_resolution = 0.05f ;
:acknowledgment = "Funded by the Copernicus Climate Change Service. Use of these data
should acknowledge the Copernicus Climate Change Service" ;
:creator_name = "Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)" ;
:creator_email = "science.leader@esa-sst-cci.org" ;
:creator_processing_institution = "These data were produced on the JASMIN infrastructure at
STFC as part of the C3S project" ;
:creator_url = "https://climate.copernicus.eu/" ;
```



```
:project = "Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)" ;  
:publisher_name = "Copernicus Climate Data Store" ;  
:publisher_url = "https://climate.copernicus.eu/" ;  
:publisher_email = "copernicus-support@ecmwf.int" ;  
:processing_level = "L4" ;  
:cdm_data_type = "grid" ;  
:product_specification_version = "SST_CCI-PSD-UKMO-201-Issue-H" ;  
:contact = "http://copernicus-support.ecmwf.int" ;  
}
```